

1 **Investigating the New Year's Eve effect: Analysis of the presence and**
2 **persistence of pyrotechnic explosive related ions in the background**
3 **using IC-ESI-MS**

4 Jesse Verbunt ^{a, b}

5 ^aNetherlands Forensic Institute, P.O. Box 24044, 2490 AA The Hague, The
6 Netherlands

7 ^bCLHC, Amsterdam Center for Forensic Science and Medicine, University of
8 Amsterdam, P.O. Box 94157, 1090 GD Amsterdam, The Netherlands

9 *Correspondence and requests should be addressed to: Carlos Martín-Alberca
10 (c.martin.alberca@nfi.minvenj.nl)

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Investigating the New Year's Eve effect: Analysis of the presence and
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Master Forensic Science – University of Amsterdam - 36 EC

Name: ing. Jesse Verbunt
Student ID: 11384492
Research institute: Netherlands Forensic Institute
Contact: jesseverbunt@hotmail.com
Period: 01/2018 – 08/2018
Supervisor: Dr. Carlos Martín Alberca (NFI)
Examiner: Prof. Dr. Arian van Asten (UvA / NFI)

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24 The custom of the Dutch to ignite a lot of fireworks at New Year's Eve (NYE) may
25 cause problems in the interpretations in forensic explosive casework. Similar
26 compounds as encountered in casework will fall back to earth, likely increasing
27 the background levels of these ions. This study determined the presence,
28 significance and relevance of this effect which we named the New Year's Eve
29 Effect (NYEE). Employees of the Explosives group of the Netherlands Forensic
30 Institute (NFI) collected samples before NYE (reference) and at 7 intervals in
31 January by swabbing an A5 sized surface on different objects using an
32 isopropanol swab. After sample preparation according to a standard procedure of
33 the NFI, the samples were analysed using a new state-of-the-art ACN-enhanced
34 stepwise gradient ion chromatography coupled to electron spray ionisation mass
35 spectrometry (IC-ESI-MS) anion method. It is observed that the NYEE is present
36 and tendencies can be recognized for ions relatable to fireworks like chloride,
37 nitrate, sulfate, thiocyanate, thiosulfate, chlorate and perchlorate. Although the
38 effect is present, only 1 out of 84 changes in ionic concentrations analysed
39 seems to be statistically significant. The significant change is found for
40 perchlorate present on lamp posts. These results are obtained under the specific
41 conditions as present during this study. Whether the effect has an impact on
42 forensic casework depends in the case related context, less decreasing
43 influences or higher pyrotechnic activity will lead to a higher significance and
44 therefore larger possible impact on case work.

45 Keywords: Consumer fireworks, forensic analysis, ion chromatography, mass
46 spectrometry, New Year's Eve Effect, pyrotechnics.

47 **1. INTRODUCTION**

48 Igniting fireworks at midnight on the first day of the New Year could be seen as
49 a big tradition in the Netherlands. Colourful pyrotechnics, worth millions of
50 euros, will colour the sky for minutes, or even hours [1]. This evening full of joy
51 has some downsides as well. Trauma surgeons stated that 95 people got injured
52 after the use of fireworks or as being a bystander (35% of the cases) at New
53 Year's Eve (NYE) 2018. 50% of the cases involved legal fireworks, and the other
54 half consisted out of cases involving illegal fireworks and cases where no
55 information was made available from [2]. Another effect that is inseparable to
56 the use of fireworks is the damage it can bring forward on common goods and
57 properties. In the Netherlands the damages of the celebration of 2017/2018
58 were estimated at 13 million euros [3]. Besides the direct impact on public
59 health and the public space, it brings a forensic relevant consequence and
60 challenge forward as well. After ignition and deflagration, the residues of these
61 pyrotechnics will fall down back to the ground as Grima et al. showed in their
62 study [4]. It was observed that the particles originating from the fireworks were
63 found on spectators of a firework show and on objects surrounding the display
64 site (approximately 150 meters away, in wind direction). Grima also stated that
65 wind has a large impact on the collection of the samples, causing a dispersion of
66 the particle population [4]. The particles returned to Earth can persist until they
67 are removed or, for example, are flushed away by precipitation. It is not known
68 what the concentration levels and persistence of these chemicals are and
69 whether these compounds could be influencing the evidence interpretation in
70 casework. With this uncertainty, a problem for forensic experts involved
71 pyrotechnic casework rises.

72 Nowadays, scientists of the Netherlands Forensic Institute (NFI), which are
73 investigating an explosive related incident, for example an attack on an ATM
74 using inorganic explosives, will include a caveat in their reports when reporting
75 on a crime in the first weeks of the year. This caveat will refer to the fact that
76 the found pyrotechnic traces could originate from the attack or, completely
77 unrelated, from the NYE celebrations. Because of this, there is a need for the
78 determination of background levels of this type of traces and to determine
79 whether there is a change in background levels and to what extent this may
80 persist. The change in background levels of ions related to pyrotechnics after
81 NYE, we define as the "New Year's Eve Effect" (NYEE).

82 A forensic tool for the classification, identification and individualisation [5] is
83 chemical profiling, as possible and tried for several explosives and pyrotechnics
84 [6]. Chemical profiling of explosives relies on the differences and/or similarities
85 between sources of residue and between the material of interest and the
86 background levels of those specific compounds. One could find several anions in
87 residues of pyrotechnic explosives like perchlorate, chlorate, nitrate, but also
88 cations like sodium, strontium and a variety of transition metals [7], of which
89 some may only originate from the pyrotechnic events. Before this profiling can
90 take place, it is important to know the background levels. However, only a few
91 studies [8, 9] were published on the matter of background values of compounds
92 related to explosives, performed in the United Kingdom (UK) and in the United
93 States (US). Lahoda et al. [9] points out that none were published on something
94 like the NYEE or specific on pyrotechnics. Currently, the survey of Walker et al.
95 [8], dated from 2001, is used for interpretation of the results by experts of the
96 NFI.

97 Pyrotechnic traces can be analysed using a large variety of methods, being
98 electron microscopy, atomic and molecular spectroscopy, potentiometric testing
99 or chromatographic techniques like gas chromatography and liquid
100 chromatography often coupled to a mass spectrometer (MS) and other
101 techniques like capillary electrophoresis and ion chromatography (IC) [8].

102 In this study a new ACN-enhanced stepwise gradient ion chromatography
103 coupled to electron spray ionisation mass spectrometry (IC-ESI-MS) method is
104 used as described by Martín-Alberca et al. [11]. The method is more sensitive
105 than previous methods and is currently also capable to identify 27 anions within
106 30 minutes. At the time of this research, the method was able to detect and
107 quantify 16 anions using the IC's conductivity detector (CD) and to identify 25
108 anions by use of the single quadrupole MS, according to the European
109 Commission directive on identification points in analytical chemistry [12].

110 In order to determine the presence of the NYEE three main questions should be
111 answered: "Are values of certain chemicals related to fireworks in the
112 environment increased after NYE?" "Is the observed effect significant?" And:
113 "How long does the effect persist?" In order to obtain the information needed for
114 indicating a possible NYEE, several experts of the NFI participated in taking
115 samples of different locations and objects, over time in order to determine the
116 concentrations of ions of interest on the sampled areas. The samples were taken
117 at different intervals in the first month of 2018 to monitor the possible increase
118 and decrease of ion concentrations encountered after the NYE. Reference
119 samples were taken as well in order to establish the background levels of ions in
120 that particular area before NYE.

121 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

122 2.1 Chemicals, standards and materials

123 As described before, the method of Martín-Alberca et al. [11] is used for analysis
124 of the samples. Samples and standards were made using ultra-pure Milli-Q water
125 (resistivity of 18.2 M Ω ·cm at 21°C obtained from a Veolia Water ELGA system.
126 Acetonitrile (ACN) was obtained from LiChroSolv and sodium carbonate (0.5 M),
127 sodium bicarbonate (<99.7%) and sulfuric acid (5 M) were obtained from Fluka.

128 1000 ppm standard solutions were made from 25 target anions and out of these
129 stock solutions a mixed 25 anions standard was obtained in several
130 concentrations. **Table 1** displays the target ions and the salts/acids/compounds
131 they are produced out of.

132 **Table 1** Overview of the 25 target ions, their formula and origin. All substances were obtained
133 from Sigma Aldrich, Switzerland.

Ion	Formula	Origin (salt or acid)
Threonate	C ₄ H ₈ O ₅ ⁻	Threonic acid
Acetate	CH ₃ COO ⁻	Ammonium acetate
Glycerate	C ₃ H ₆ O ₄ ⁻	D-Glyceric acid
Iodate	IO ₃ ⁻	Potassium iodate
Fluoride	F ⁻	Sodium Fluoride
Lactate	C ₃ H ₆ O ₃ ⁻	Lactic acid
Formate	HCO ₂ ⁻	IC standard, Calcium formate
Bromate	BrO ₃ ⁻	Sodium bromate
Chloride	Cl ⁻	IC standard, Sodium chloride
Cyanate	OCN ⁻	Sodium cyanate
Nitrite	NO ₂ ⁻	IC standard, Sodium nitrite
Chlorate	ClO ₃ ⁻	Potassium chlorate
Azide	N ₃ ⁻	Sodium azide
Nitrate	NO ₃ ⁻	IC standard, Sodium nitrate
Benzoate	C ₆ H ₅ COO ⁻	Potassium benzoate
Phosphate	PO ₄ ²⁻	IC standard, Disodium phosphate
Tartrate	C ₄ H ₆ O ₅ ²⁻	Tartaric acid
Sulfate	SO ₄ ²⁻	IC standard, Sodium sulfate
Oxalate	C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	Oxalic acid
Phthalate	C ₆ H ₄ (COO ⁻) ₂	Phthalic acid
Thiosulfate	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	Potassium thiosulfate
Thiocyanate	SCN ²⁻	Potassium thiocyanate
Chromate	CrO ₄ ²⁻	Sodium chromate
Perchlorate	ClO ₄ ⁻	Potassium Perchlorate
Iso-phthalate	C ₆ H ₄ (COO ⁻) ₂	Iso-phthalic acid

134

135 All volunteers were provided with sample kits containing lab clamps (BVDA),
136 vinyl gloves (VWR), swabs containing 70% isopropanol (B. Braun), sample jars
137 (Thermo Fisher), frame for indicating sample area (Schinfa) and an instruction
138 sheet. For each sample that had to be taken, all materials were present in the
139 kit. The sample kit is depicted in **Fig. 1**.

140

141 **Fig. 1** The NYEE sampling kit for volunteers, containing: 1. bag, 2. instruction sheet, 3. sample set
 142 for reference samples, 4. spare materials, 5. sample sets for NYEE samples, 6. A5 sample frame,
 143 7. waste bag, 8. clamps, 9. swabs, 10. vinyl gloves, 11. sample jars, and 12. registration forms.

144 2.2 Instrumentation and analytical conditions

145 Analysis was performed using a Metrohm 850 Professional IC coupled to a
 146 Metrohm 863 Compact Auto sampler. The analytes were detected using a
 147 Metrohm IC CD and mass spectra were obtained using a Waters® SQ Detector
 148 2, single quadrupole, Z-Spray ESI-MS. The system was controlled and the data
 149 was processed using MagIC Net Professional v.3.1 obtained from Metrohm and
 150 MassLynx v.4.1 software obtained from Waters.

151 The IC was equipped with a sample loop of 20 μL , a Metrohm Metrosep A Trap 1
 152 guard column (100 x 4.0 mm) combined with a Metrosep A Supp 5 column (250
 153 x 4.0 mm) and a Metrohm CD detector and was equipped with a Metrohm MSM
 154 Rotor A 3-step column suppressor, using a 50 mM of sulphuric acid in ultra-pure
 155 Milli-Q water solution and a 30:70 mixture of ACN in ultra-pure Milli-Q water.

156 The IC was used in gradient mode of which the steps are listed in **Table 2**. The
 157 eluents for the IC were composed out of 34% (A) and 10% (B) ACN in ultra-pure
 158 Milli-Q water. Both mixtures contained 5 mM sodium carbonate and 4.8 mM
 159 sodium bicarbonate.

160

161 **Table 2** The ACN-enhanced step gradient method of the IC. During analysis, a flow of 0.8 mL/min
 162 and temperature of 30°C was kept constant throughout all gradient steps.

Time (min)	Eluent A (%)	Eluent B (%)	Curve
0.00	0	100	-
11.20	0	100	Step gradient
15.70	100	0	Linear
44.00	0	100	Step
75.00	0	100	-

163

164 The MS was operated in negative mode (ESI-). Besides scan channels in the m/z
 165 range 20.00 to 500.00 at different cone voltages, individual ion channels were
 166 monitored as well. For each target ion a scan-window was opened around the
 167 time of elution [11]. The capillary voltage was 2 kV and the standard cone
 168 voltage was 20 V, but was set per compound according to Martín-Alberca et al.
 169 [11]. The used desolvation gas flow was set on 1200 L/h at a desolvation
 170 temperature of 600 °C.

171 2.3 Samples and sample locations

172 A total of 130 samples were taken, of which 24 were reference samples and 106
 173 were samples taken after NYE. **Fig. 2** shows the distributions of object types
 174 amongst the data set.

175

176 **Fig. 2** Overview of the sampled objects and their abundance in the sample set.

177 The 8 sample areas were located in the Haaglanden – Rotterdam region (6),
 178 Hollands Midden (1) and in Twente (1), as displayed in **Fig. 3**. The categories
 179 mentioned are generic object categories. One should take into account that
 180 within a category several discrepancies may occur. For example, there are
 181 multiple materials, placed under specific conditions and coverage, which fall in
 182 the category front coping.

183

184

185 **Fig. 3** Sample locations throughout the Netherlands [13].

186 Of the total of 130 samples, 14 samples were discarded for several reasons. The
 187 first reason was the lack a reference sample in a particular sample category (by
 188 default), resulting in the discarding of 7 samples. These samples were taken into
 189 account for the general interpretation, but not for the object specific analysis.
 190 The second reason was that volunteers switched to an object without reference
 191 samples and/or switching to/sampling extraordinary (dirty) objects out of
 192 curiosity (7 samples). These samples were not taken into account for
 193 interpretation.

194 **2.4 Sampling method**

195 The sample frame was placed upon a surface and the medical swab was
 196 removed from its package using the clamps. The surface was swabbed within the
 197 sample frame. Subsequently, the swab was transferred to the sample jar. Before
 198 NYE three reference samples per volunteer were taken, and the NYEE samples
 199 were taken in duplicate at January 1st, 3rd, 5th, 10th, 17th, 24th and 31st. All
 200 samples were coded and submitted for analysis.

201 **2.5 Sample preparation and analysis**

202 In accordance with NFI SOP 161501 [14], 10 mL of ultra-pure water was added
 203 to the samples and the samples were placed in an ultrasonic bath for 10
 204 minutes. The sample was transferred using a syringe with a 45 µm filter to the
 205 corresponding test tube.

206 1 mL of the sample was transferred to an IC vial and injected into the IC-MS.

207

208

209 2.6 Blank experiments

210 The blank experiments had the aims to test the sample preparation materials, to
211 provide a new positive control for the extraction step in the analysis and to
212 obtain qualitative recovery results of the used sampling method.

213 First, in triplicate step-by-step blanks were taken of each step of the sampling
214 process using 2 mL of Milli-Q water. After taking a sample, all steps, as
215 mentioned in paragraph 2.3, were followed according to NFI SOP 161501 [14].
216 In order to obtain a positive control, 100 µl of 10 ppm 25 anion standard was
217 directly pipetted on a swab and placed in the sample jar.

218 In the blank samples low concentrations of the critical ions chloride, sulfate and
219 nitrate were found. These values were subtracted from the experimental values
220 in order to obtain the true concentrations of ions present in the sample. The
221 anions present in the blank samples are also found by Walker et al. [8] in their
222 study, but higher values were observed in this study. Thiocyanate, thiosulfate,
223 chlorate and perchlorate were not observed in any of the blank samples. The
224 concentrations are displayed in **Table 3**. All spiked ions were recovered after
225 analysis.

226 **Table 3** Average concentrations of present critical ions found in blank samples.

Sample	Chloride (ppm)	Nitrate (ppm)	Sulfate (ppm)
Milli-Q water	0.001	0.004	0.000
Syringe	0.001	0.003	0.001
Syringe + filter	0.109	0.003	0.002
Syringe + filter + jar	0.110	0.003	0.001
Swab extract	0.103	0.007	0.120
Vinyl gloves (usage)	0.117	0.007	0.063

227

228 2.7 Data analysis

229 Sample data was separated by object types sampled. Per object type the data
230 was divided into three categories: before New Year's Eve (reference sample;
231 Ref), the first half of January and the second half of January. The assumption
232 was made that any changes observed after the 15th of January were not caused
233 directly by the NYEE, because of affecting conditions as spoken of in paragraph
234 3.3.1. Grima et al. [4] performed analysis after 90 minutes, but because of the
235 size of the dataset obtained for this work, it was needed to make the sample
236 size per time span bigger. It should be mentioned that it is not stated that
237 changes observed in the first half of January are irrefutable related to the NYEE.

238 Raw data was analysed using the mentioned software in two ways. The IC data
239 was used for detection/screening and quantification of compounds and the MS
240 data was used for identification/confirmation. A compound was called 'present'
241 when it was observable in both the IC chromatogram and MS m/z specific data.
242 Per ion the target fragments were monitored in several channels, making it
243 possible to reach the needed amount of identification points [12]. For the MS
244 data the following criteria had to be met because of the use of a, at the time of
245 the study, partially validated quantification method:

- 246 • S/N < 3: Rejected
- 247 • S/N 3-7: Examiner's opinion, critical review

248 • S/N 7+: Accepted, but screening by examiner

249 Chemical presence, after identification and quantification, of the anions were
250 translated to four general categories:

- 251 • Not detected: the compound was not detected in the sample;
- 252 • > LOD MS: the compound was identified by the MS, but not detected
253 using the IC. Quantification was not possible, but concentrations are
254 estimated as < 0.01 - 0.001 ppm;
- 255 • > LOQ CD: the compound was identified using MS and detected and
256 quantified using the IC's CD in a concentration < 1 ppm;
- 257 • > 1 ppm: the compound was identified using MS and detected and
258 quantified using the IC in a concentration > 1 ppm.

259 Graphs were obtained per ion plotting the abundance percentage of the general
260 categories.

261 The significance is determined by the use of the Wilcoxon rank sum test for the
262 analysis of a shift in median of the data set in combination with the Bonferroni
263 correction for multiple comparisons and the family-wise error rate [15, 16].
264 Three comparisons were carried out. The reference samples were compared by
265 their median to the samples of the first half of January in order to see the effect
266 of NYE. Besides this, the expected decrease is analysed by comparing the first
267 and second half of January. Whether the values are back to the reference values
268 is tested by comparing the values of the second half of January with the
269 references values. The analysis is performed using and source file in MS Excel
270 and a R script ran with R studio on R i386 3.2.2. The used script is provided in
271 the supplementary data.

272 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

273 **3.1 Selection of ions**

274 Although the used method is currently able to identify and quantify up to 25
275 anions, at the moment of this research the method was not optimized for all of
276 these ions. Therefore the ions acetate, azide, cyanate, fluoride, glycerate,
277 iodate, lactate, nitrite, and threonate were discarded from the analysis. Besides
278 this it was observed that 12 ions were detected in most samples and therefore
279 were deemed not to be specific. These ions were only reported in case of finding
280 unexpected high concentrations. Extracting these ions from the target list, 7 ions
281 were marked as critical ions: chloride, nitrate, sulfate, thiocyanate, thiosulfate,
282 chlorate and perchlorate.

283 These ions were deemed critical because of their abundance and direct relation
284 to explosives, either in pre and/or post blast residues.

285 Chloride (Cl⁻) is a highly abundant anion trough out the environment and can be
286 used as an additive salt in explosive compositions [17]. Besides this, chloride is
287 a possible product of the reduction of chlorate and perchlorate [18-20].

288 Martín-Alberca et al. [18] described the reactions as depicted in **Equation 1** and
289 **Equation 2**.

290

291 **Equation 1** Reaction of the reduction of chlorate to chloride [18]

292 **Equation 2** Reaction of the reduction of perchlorate to chloride [18]

293 Chloride can also be encountered in the post blast residue of
294 chlorate/perchlorate - sugar compositions and in flash powder based on chlorate
295 combined with, for example, aluminium [18, 21]

296 Nitrate (NO_3^-) can be found in several explosive/pyrotechnic post blast residues
297 and compositions as black powder [18, 21-25], flash powder [26-28] and
298 ammonium nitrate based explosives [17, 29, 30].

299 Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) is to be found in post blast residues of sulfur containing
300 pyrotechnic compositions, mainly black powder compositions [21-25] and a flash
301 powder composition described by Hutchinson [21].

302 Martín-Alberca et al. [18] described the reaction as depicted in **Equation 3**.

303 **Equation 3** Reaction of the oxidation of sulfur to sulfate [18]

304 Thiocyanate (SCN^-) used to be used in pyrotechnic snakes [31], but after
305 prohibition by law of the mercury thiocyanate based pyrotechnics it is nowadays
306 found in post blast residues of improvised explosive devices according to Martín-
307 Alberca et al. [18] and Hutchinson [21]. Martín-Alberca et al. [18] describes that
308 thiocyanate can be formed in two ways under combustion conditions, described
309 in **Equation 4** and **Equation 5**.

310 **Equation 4** Reaction of the formation of thiocyanate as result of the combustion reaction between
311 cyanate and sulfur [18]

312 **Equation 5** Reaction of the formation of thiocyanate as result of the combustion reaction between
313 cyanate and thiosulfate [18]

314 Thiosulfate ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$) can be found after the deflagration of black powder and
315 sulfur containing flash powder [21-25]. Its oxidation product, sulfate, is also
316 listed as a critical ion. Thiosulfate can be formed out of the reaction between
317 elemental sulfur and its sulfite ion, which is depicted in **Equation 6**. The partial
318 reduction of sulfate or the partial oxidation of sulfides are two other path ways
319 for the formation of thiosulfate [18].

320 **Equation 6** Reaction of the formation of thiosulfate out of sulfite and elemental sulfur [18]

321

322 Chlorate (ClO_3^-) is present in some types of flash powder compositions [21, 32]
323 and in chlorate – sugar compositions [21]. Chlorate can also be encountered
324 after the reduction of perchlorate [18, 20].

325 Martín-Alberca et al. [18] described the reaction as depicted in **Equation 7**.

326 **Equation 7** Reaction of the reduction of perchlorate to chlorate [18]

327 Perchlorate (ClO_4^-), the last critical anion, is mainly found in flash powder [33-
328 35] and perchlorate – sugar compositions [21] but can also be found in some
329 alternative formulations of black powder [25, 36]. As mentioned before,
330 perchlorate can be reduced to chlorate and chloride, resulting in differences in
331 pre and post blast residue composition.

332 The latter four ions are deemed the most interesting for this purpose.
333 Thiocyanate and thiosulfate are seen as well-defined markers for explosive post
334 blast residue. Chlorate and perchlorate are observed in many often encountered
335 pyrotechnic compositions [18, 21].

336 The critical ions were always identified and quantified if present above the LOQ
337 of the CD in the samples.

338 **3.2 Chemical data**

339 *3.2.1 General overview*

340 A graph was obtained from the chemical data on the samples before (reference)
341 and after NYE (January 1st – 31st), as displayed in **Fig. 4**. It is visualised that the
342 presence of all ions is increased after NYE. Chloride, nitrate and sulfate were
343 present in all samples (be it from several sources not related to NYE), but in a
344 small fraction of the samples the concentration was negligible after blank-
345 subtraction, causing a small percentage of these ion to be marked as not
346 detected, as shown in **Fig. 4**. Perchlorate was found in very low levels before
347 NYE in 13% of the samples and in 54% of the samples after NYE. Of these
348 samples, 2% contained perchlorate in a concentration between 0.001 ppm and 1
349 ppm. In about half of the samples after NYE (52%) perchlorate was detected by
350 the MS, but not quantified due to the very low concentrations. Before NYE this
351 was the case in only 13% of the samples. Chlorate was quantified using the CD
352 in 42% of the cases before NYE and 61% after NYE. Besides the CD detection,
353 chlorate was also detected in unquantifiable concentrations in 21% and 17% of
354 the samples for respectively before and after NYE. Thiocyanate was observed
355 only in unquantifiable concentrations, in 21% of the sample before NYE and in
356 34% of the samples after NYE. Thiosulfate was observed only in unquantifiable
357 concentrations as well, in 4% of the sample before NYE and in 14% of the
358 samples after NYE.

359

360 **Fig. 4** Comparison of the distribution of the concentration categories of the critical ions before
 361 (Ref) and after NYE (NYE).

362 Taking everything into account, a tendency of increases of ion concentrations is
 363 observed for all critical ions. Even though in the cases of the direct pyrotechnic
 364 related ions thiocyanate, thiosulfate and perchlorate the differences were very
 365 small, the applied sampling strategy and analytical method are able to detect
 366 these differences. Similar trends were observed for most other ions as well. The
 367 raw data is available via a supplementary data request, the data used in this
 368 paper is provided in the supplementary data.

369 One should be aware of the down side of this way of data presentation; the size
 370 of the categories and the possibility of overestimating the value and significance
 371 of the results. For example, 61% of the samples after NYE contains chlorate in
 372 concentrations < 1 ppm but higher than the limit of quantification of the IC.
 373 When looking closer to these results it is observed that 60% of those samples
 374 contain chlorate of levels below 10 ppb. Only 16% of these samples have
 375 chlorate levels above 0.1 ppm.

376 3.2.2 General overview per ion

377 Comparison to the literature learns that chloride is found in 85% of the analysed
 378 samples by Walker et al. [8] with a concentration range between 0 and ~500
 379 ppm. On an object type that is analysed in both this study as by Walker et al.
 380 [8], namely traffic signs, chloride is observed with an average of ~15 ppm with
 381 a maximum of ~80 ppm. In the study of Lahoda et al. [9] 58% of the samples
 382 tested positive on chloride with a median concentration of 3 ppm and a
 383 maximum of 1100 ppm. It is observed that although chloride is found in almost all
 384 samples, the mean (3.9 ppm) and de median (0.9 ppm) were much lower than
 385 in other studies, but was found in 100% of the reference samples and in 90% of
 386 the NYEE (**Fig. 4**).

387

388 It should be noted that there are differences between the mentioned references
389 and this study. So used the references a sample area of twice [9] and four times
390 the size [8] of the NYEE study. Also the used analytical techniques differ per
391 study. Walker et al. [8] used an IC, but a different system for general anions,
392 perchlorate, sugars and cations. Lahoda [9] made use of an capillary zone
393 electrophoresis system [9]. Although, in terms of quantification, both techniques
394 should give an similar outcome, in both references the size of the sample loop is
395 not mentioned. The sample loop plays a large role in the end concentration
396 obtained, making this hard to compare. Another difference is the swabs used.
397 Walker et al. [9] used water-wetted cotton wool swabs and Lahoda et al. [9]
398 used cotton balls for swabbing (it is not stated whether the swabs were dry of
399 wetted). The extraction procedures used were a extraction of the swab using 5
400 mL of deionized water while being compressed by the use of a Pasteur pipette,
401 and later diluted to an end volume of 10 mL, by Walker et al. [8] Lahoda et al.
402 [9] extracted the samples using 1 mL of deionized water and centrifuging the
403 samples at 1000 rpm for 8 minutes. Before comparison, the values of the
404 references were converted to units used in this study.

405 Nitrate was detected in 45% of the samples by Walker et al. [8] and in 17% of
406 the samples by Lahoda et al. [9], against a 100% in reference samples and in
407 96% of the NYEE samples (**Fig. 4**). Maximum concentrations vary ~8 ppm in
408 this study to 28 ppm (a maximum of 2.5 ppm on signs) [8] and 110 ppm [9].
409 For nitrate, the median was found on 3 ppm by Lahoda et al. [9] and on 0.09
410 ppm in this study. Even if corrected for the sampling surface, the values are still
411 a factor 10 lower than found in the literature.

412 Sulfate was detected in 95% of the samples by Walker et al. [8] and in 31% of
413 the samples by Lahoda et al. [9] against 87% of the reference samples and in
414 84% of the NYEE samples in this study (**Fig. 4**). Concentrations vary between 0
415 and 1900 ppm, with a median of 10 ppm found by Lahoda et al. [9] compared to
416 0.2 ppm in this study.

417 Thiocyanate was not found in any of the samples by Walker et al. [8] and in only
418 1% of the samples of Lahoda et al. [9]. In this study very low concentrations of
419 thiocyanate (> LOD MS) were found in 21% of the reference samples and in
420 34% of the NYEE samples (**Fig. 4**).

421 Thiosulfate was not taken into account by both referenced studies. The
422 compound was found in 4% of the reference samples and in 14% of the NYEE
423 samples in very low concentrations (> LOD MS) (**Fig. 4**).

424 Chlorate was found in just 2% of the samples from Walker et al. [8] in the range
425 of 0.04 – 0.3 ppm. Lahoda et al. [9] detected chlorate also in 2% of the samples
426 with a maximum of 19 ppm and a median of 2 ppm. In this study, chlorate was
427 found in low concentrations in 62% of the reference samples and in 78% of the
428 NYEE samples (**Fig. 4**) with a maximum of 0.375 ppm and a median of 0.003
429 ppm. The values observed are (much) lower than the values in the literature but
430 occur more often.

431 Perchlorate was not found in any of the samples by Walker et al. [8] and in 1%
432 of the samples by Lahoda et al. [9] with a maximum concentration of 15 ppm
433 with a median of 1 ppm. Perchlorate was observed in 13% of the reference
434 samples (in very low concentrations) and in 64% of the NYEE samples, of which

435 2% was quantified using the CD (**Fig. 4**). The maximum concentration observed
436 was 0.417 ppm but was not detected in the majority of the samples (the median
437 of the sample set was determined at 0 ppm).

438 It is observed that the concentrations of the ions of interest are detected in
439 lower concentrations as the studies in 2001 and 2008, even after correction of
440 the sample areas. Although the fact that the concentrations were present in
441 lower concentration, their abundance in the sample set was higher. It is
442 probable that the techniques in this day and age are more sensitive to detect
443 very low concentrations of these ions. The LOD of the used method is in the
444 range between 1 – 100 ppb, where the range of Lahoda et al. [9] is between 1 -
445 15 ppm. Walker et al. [8] did not publish the obtained LOD of their method.

446 *3.2.3 Time related overview per ion*

447 The concentrations (categories) per ion were monitored in three time periods:
448 before NYE, as a reference, and in the first and second half of January. The
449 assumption was made that when NYE has an effect on the background levels,
450 this would not be first observed after the 15th of January because of
451 degrading/decreasing effects of for example the weather or chemical reactions
452 and because of research of Grima et al. [4] showing that particle deposition
453 occurs rather quickly. The time span could be found rather large, but because of
454 size of the data set this was deemed the best approach. The results are shown in
455 **Fig. 5**. Expected tendencies show an increase of ion presence after NYE in de
456 first half of January and a decrease of ions in the second half of January. These
457 tendencies were observed for chloride, sulfate, thiocyanate, thiosulfate and
458 perchlorate. For nitrate an increase of 6% was observed for samples containing
459 more than 1 ppm of nitrate. Chlorate was found in trace levels (> LOQ CD) in
460 6% more samples in the second half of January than in the first half. This
461 increase is mainly caused by samples containing < 10 ppb of chlorate. Based on
462 these results it is observed that, although tendencies of changes in
463 concentrations are present, the values in the second half of January are not back
464 to the values obtained from the reference samples for the ions thiocyanate,
465 thiosulfate, chlorate and perchlorate.

466

468

469 **Fig. 5** Abundance of the concentration categories per critical ion divided over three time intervals:
 470 reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and from January 16th till
 471 January 31st.

472 3.2.4 Object dependent analysis

473 Analysis of data showed a large variability between sources. Certain object types
 474 seem to be more prone to the presence of certain ions. Chloride, for example is
 475 more often observed in higher concentrations on windows and building materials
 476 than on other objects sampled in this study. Also, sulfate and nitrate are
 477 observed more in higher concentrations on windows than on other object
 478 categories. Another factor that could be involved is the effectivity of the
 479 sampling strategy on the different objects. It is described in literature that on
 480 certain surfaces the transfer between swab and object is more efficient than on
 481 others [37-39]. Being this, amongst many variables in the sampling taking, a
 482 variable that is controllable, the data of the ions, as shown in **Fig. 5**, is
 483 separated by the object type the sample has been taken from. All samples were
 484 connected to one of the four general categories: windows, traffic signs (including
 485 street name signs), building materials (materials as wooden covers, front
 486 coping, walls, and objects that are on and around buildings that fall not in the
 487 other categories), and lamp posts.

488 Analysis of chloride, **Fig. 6**, showed that the presumed effect, an increase of
 489 concentration in the first half of January pertaining to the reference samples and
 490 a decrease in the second half of January, is visible for traffic signs, building
 491 materials and lamp posts. The samples originating from windows seem to show
 492 a continuous increase of concentration over the three time periods. It should be
 493 mentioned that only one random sampling spot per measurement was used, the
 494 observed increase could be caused by with-in source variation or by chemical
 495 reactions or human activities.

Chloride

496

497 **Fig. 6** Abundance of the concentration categories of chloride per object type, divided over three
 498 time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and from
 499 January 16th till January 31st.

500 Analysis of nitrate, **Fig. 7**, showed a similar tendency for samples originating
 501 from windows as observed for chloride. For all other object types, all samples
 502 contained concentrations < 1 ppm of nitrate, with the exception of 13% of the
 503 samples originating from traffics signs and 14% of the samples originating from
 504 lamp posts in the first half January.

Nitrate

505

506 **Fig. 7** Abundance of the concentration categories of nitrate per object type, divided over three
 507 time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and from
 508 January 16th till January 31st.

509 Analysis of sulfate, **Fig. 8**, showed a similar tendency for samples originating
 510 from windows as observed for chloride and nitrate. Further it is observed that
 511 nitrate is present in all samples of traffic signs in concentrations below 1 ppm.
 512 No increase is observed after NYE. Sulfate values increased after NYE,
 513 encountered in 25% of the samples taken from building materials and 14% of
 514 sample originating from lamp posts. It is also observed that in both mentioned
 515 categories no sulfate levels of > 1 ppm are detected after the 15th of January.

Sulfate

516

517 **Fig. 8** Abundance of the concentration categories of sulfate per object type, divided over three
 518 time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and from
 519 January 16th till January 31st.

520 Analysis of thiocyanate, **Fig. 9**, showed that this compound is never found in
 521 concentrations that could be quantified by the IC, it could be stated that the
 522 samples contained thiocyanate in low-ppb levels. Although the low
 523 concentrations, some changes over time were observed. An increase after NYE
 524 of this ion is observed for all objects except traffic signs. It is also observed that
 525 the concentration of this ion is decreasing after the 15th of January, the lastly
 526 mentioned object type excepted from this. The samples originating from traffic
 527 signs show a different tendency than the other object types. After relatively
 528 steady values from the reference and the first half of January samples, the
 529 amount of samples containing low traces of thiocyanate doubled. No cause for
 530 this increase has been found.

Thiocyanate

531

532 **Fig. 9** Abundance of the concentration categories of thiocyanate per object type, divided over
 533 three time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and
 534 from January 16th till January 31st.

535 Analysis of thiosulfate, **Fig. 10**, showed that this compound is never found in
 536 concentrations that could be quantified by the IC, comparable to the values of
 537 thiocyanate. Although the low concentrations, some changes over time were
 538 observed. For windows and lamp posts, it is observed that the amount of
 539 samples containing traces of thiosulfate is increased after NYE and that in the
 540 second half of the month this value decreases again. For both traffic signs and
 541 building materials it is observed that over time the amount of samples
 542 containing thiosulfate is increased. No cause for this increase has been found.

543

Thiosulfate

544

545 **Fig. 10** Abundance of the concentration categories of thiosulfate per object type, divided over
 546 three time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and
 547 from January 16th till January 31st.

548 Analysis of chlorate, **Fig. 11**, showed that chlorate is found in 62% of the
 549 reference samples and in 78% of the post NYE samples. As mentioned before,
 550 the chlorate levels in those samples are rather low, 60% contains less than 10
 551 ppb of chlorate. It is observed that whether a certain sample falls in one of the
 552 concentrations categories is very fluctuating, but the distribution of samples
 553 originating from lamp posts is rather stable. An increase of samples containing
 554 quantifiable amounts of chlorate after NYE is observed for samples originating
 555 from windows and building materials. This trend continued in the second half of
 556 January, which makes it illogical to connect this directly to the NYEE. Causes
 557 may be found in the persistence of chlorate on the mentioned object or a
 558 cumulative effect from other sources. Further it is observed that all reference
 559 samples originating from traffic signs contained quantifiable amounts of chlorate,
 560 which is twice as high as compared to the first half of January samples. In the
 561 second half of January the size of this category is increased again to 83%. The
 562 data originates from 2 volunteers (n = 19) and both subjects contributes to the
 563 difference in the first half of January.

Chlorate

564

565 **Fig. 11** Abundance of the concentration categories of chlorate per object type, divided over three
 566 time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and from
 567 January 16th till January 31st.

568 Analysis of perchlorate, **Fig. 12**, showed that the compound is rare to be found
 569 in high concentrations. Only in samples originating from windows and lamp posts
 570 in the first half of January contain concentrations above the limit of
 571 quantification, respectively 6.7% and 4.5%. In none of the reference nor the
 572 second half of January samples, a quantifiable amount of perchlorate is found.
 573 The samples from all objects types, except windows, follow the expected
 574 tendency. The amount of samples containing traces of perchlorate increased
 575 from 66% to 85%. The found traces are below the limit of quantification, but
 576 could originate from migration of the higher concentrated areas as sampled in
 577 the first half of January.

Perchlorate

578

579 **Fig. 12** Abundance of the concentration categories of perchlorate per object type, divided over
 580 three time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and
 581 from January 16th till January 31st.

582 An overview of the abundance of the concentration categories per object type of
 583 all ions divided over the three time intervals are listed in **Fig. A1** till **Fig. A4**,
 584 shown in appendix I.

585 **3.3 Interpretation of data**

586 *3.3.1 Affecting conditions and other variables*

587 There are several presumed conditions that may have an effect on the physical
 588 adsorption of ions on the surface as well as on the persistence of these ions.
 589 Wallace described that the persistence will be influenced by the surface type, as
 590 well as on the environmental conditions and activity after the time of the
 591 incident [40]. Further the 'ease of transfer' is mentioned as an influencing factor.
 592 This transfer may include, for example, the transfer of ions from an initial
 593 surface to a raindrop. It should be mentioned that there will be a lot of
 594 interactions (both antagonistic as protagonistic) between these affecting
 595 conditions. The option that a certain outcome is not caused by only one of the
 596 conditions, but rather by the sum of all of them should be kept open, but is not a
 597 given fact. This is an important point when trying to connect the data to certain
 598 effects. The mentioned conditions are hard to control on these 'case- samples'.
 599 By discussing the assumed affecting conditions it is intended to give a
 600 transparent and well-founded interpretation of the NYEE. More research needs to
 601 be performed to reach a well-defined impact in casework.

602

603 *Object (material)*

604 As mentioned before the type of object seems to have a large influence on
605 certain ions. It is observed that the concentrations of a certain ion are
606 undergoing large fluctuations comparing objects, possibly caused by their
607 material or exposure to fireworks. For example, in samples originating from
608 lamp posts there are no samples containing more than 1 ppm of chloride (a very
609 abundant ion), while this is at least 20% of the samples originating from other
610 object types. A similar observation is made for sulfate concentrations on
611 windows. None of reference samples contained more than 1 ppm of sulfate. After
612 NYE an increase of the presence of sulfate is observed on all object types except
613 traffic signs, which remained stable the entire month. 14% and 25% of the
614 samples from building materials and lamp posts contain more than 1 ppm of
615 sulfate, compared to the 53% of the window samples. In the second half of
616 January the sulfate values for samples from building materials and lamp posts
617 were back at the reference level. The amount of samples which contained more
618 than 1 ppm of sulfate originating from windows increased from 53% to 62%. A
619 possibility could be that this specific compound has a higher persistence on the
620 glass surfaces and is less affected by the removing or decreasing conditions.
621 Migration of ions, for example of the top of an object towards the bottom causes
622 by rainfall, has been mentioned as a possibility if the samples later on in the
623 study were taken from lower positions. The data on sample registration,
624 documented by the volunteers, does not reflect unambiguously that this is the
625 case. The mentioned properties could differ per ion and object, but are also
626 subjected to other factors as described below.

627 *Weather*

628 It is probable that precipitation is one of the main affecting factors. Since ions
629 are soluble in water, it could have a big impact on the data observed after
630 analysis. Leaching and a flush out could therefore have an impact on the
631 observed results. In **Fig. 13** two maps of the Netherlands are depicted. The
632 Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI) measured the precipitation in
633 the whole month of January. January 2018 was rather wet when compared to
634 the average precipitation over the last three decades in the month January. If
635 this is put into context for the samples of this study, it could be that the rainfall
636 (by itself) had a larger impact on the concentrations in January 2018 compared
637 to the average rainfall in the last 30 years

638

639 **Fig. 13** Comparison between the sum of the precipitation in January 2018 (A) and the average
 640 sum of the time period 1981 – 2010 (B). Please note that the scales are not the same. It is
 641 observed that more precipitation was measured during the NYEE study than the average [41, 42].

642 Another weather condition that has an impact is snow or sleet, or in fact the
 643 prevention of slippery roads. In the Netherlands municipalities are burdened to
 644 take measurements against slippery roads. One of these measurements is
 645 treating the snow or sleet with salt. The NaCl-composition of the salt could be of
 646 influence partially on the results. Three municipalities (The Hague, Rotterdam
 647 and Zoetermeer) were questioned whether their consumption of salt was high or
 648 low in January 2018 and whether the amount of salt was comparable to previous
 649 years. All municipalities mentioned that the amount of salt they used was
 650 respectively 5.5, 6.5 and 4 times lower in 2018 than in 2017. The size of this
 651 condition on the effect is not to be determined in this study.

652 *Location, position and usage*

653 The location, position and usage could also affect the concentrations found. The
 654 samples for this study are mainly taken in the western region of the
 655 Netherlands, as showed in **Fig. 3**. It might be that a location near the coast of a
 656 country will have higher concentrations of several ions than samples taken more
 657 inlands. Research from Ten Harkel [43] shows that near the coast ions as
 658 sodium and chloride are deposited via aerosols originating from the sea.
 659 Although the ratio between these two ions should be similar, chloride is found to
 660 be prone to several reactions. In winter, for example, chloride ions will form
 661 ammonium chloride aerosol under influence of the lower temperatures [43]. An
 662 accretion of ions seems to be the case, but multiple reactions and variables
 663 make it impossible to quantify this factor. It is not stated that samples taken
 664 near the coast automatically will contain more chloride than samples taken from
 665 a different place, but only that this factor may influence the amount of certain
 666 ions. A second factor could be chloride rich rainfall as described by Davies &
 667 Crosbie [44]. For the Netherlands, a study to find the spatial distribution of
 668 chloride originating from rainfall is never performed. The study from Davies &
 669 Crosbie [44] was performed in Australia and confirms this assumption, as shown

670 in **Fig. 14**. In the western region of the provinces Western Australia and Victoria
671 the concentration of chloride is higher than in the midlands.

672

673 **Fig. 14** Location of chloride in rainfall measurement sites in Australia [44]. Reprinted from Journal
674 of Hydrology, volume 561, P.J. Davies & R.S. Crosbie, Mapping the spatial distribution of chloride
675 deposition across Australia, page 78, © 2018, with permission of Elsevier.

676 Differences were observed between different locations, but this study provides
677 too little information on these conditions to make hard claims on this matter.

678 The position (placement) and usage will also affect the outcome of an analysis.
679 In **Fig. 15** three examples of locations are displayed. **Fig. 15 A** shows the
680 samples carport and attached pole. The front coping of the carport could,
681 depending on the angle of incidence of the precipitation, be covered against
682 influences of nature and against post blast residue deposition. Besides this the
683 object is not subjected to a lot of usage because of its function and height. The
684 pole of the carport is (except from the top) more exposed to nature and usage.
685 This could affect the present ions in an increasing as well as in a decreasing way.

686

687 **Fig. 15 A – C** Examples of sampling places used by the volunteers of the NYEE study: A) samples
688 were taken from the car-port (building material), B) samples were taken from both signs (traffic
689 signs), C) samples were taken from both the window and the mailbox.

690 **Fig. 15 B** shows two traffic signs that are placed perpendicular to each other.
691 Depending on the directionality of the wind there is a possibility that this will
692 affect the results of an analysis when both signs are compared. A second factor
693 of influence could be the fact that the signs are stacked. Rainfall may cause
694 migration of ions downwards on the blue sign. Because of this, it is possible that
695 the bottom sign has a higher, or slower decreasing, concentration on it that the
696 top sign. The way the signs are positioned will also play a role in the deposition
697 of the firework residues. As Grima et al. [4] described is the deposition and
698 distribution of particles also prone to the wind directionality. If the sign is placed
699 perpendicular on the wind direction it is more likely that particles can deposit on
700 the object than when it is placed in-line with the wind direction. A good
701 comparison could not be made between these signs because of the low sample
702 size for these particular locations. The data is indicating that the differences are
703 minimal, but no hard claims could be made.

704 **Fig. 15 C** displays an example of usage. A volunteer took reference samples and
705 NYEE sample till the 10th of January from the windows next to the entrance. In
706 the days after the sampling it was observed that the windows were cleaned. This

707 made the volunteer change object to the mailboxes on the left side of the
 708 building, resulting in comparison problems for the interpretations. These mail
 709 boxes were very dirty and the samples contained high concentrations of chloride
 710 and perchlorate. The concentrations of nitrate, sulfate and chlorate were higher
 711 as encountered on other samples from this volunteer.

712 In the last week of May 2018 (4 months after the NYEE sampling took place)
 713 another sample was taken to check these concerning high values. **Table 4**
 714 displays the measured concentrations of this object. These high concentrations
 715 were never observed before during this study. Possibilities for these values could
 716 be that the ions have a high persistence on the material of the mail boxes, the
 717 mail boxes are not cleaned and are covered and protected against the before
 718 mentioned affecting conditions. An external factor is also that the area in front of
 719 the object is often used to ignite fireworks, as stated by the resident. This
 720 activity near the object could result in the found concentrations, but is not
 721 proved in this particular case.

722 **Table 4** Overview of the concentrations of the critical ions found on mailboxes after a volunteer
 723 changed objects. Comparison between the NYEE samples and a follow up sampling 4 months later.

Sample	Cl ⁻ (ppm)	NO ₃ ⁻ (ppm)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (ppm)	SCN ²⁻ (ppm)	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ (ppm)	ClO ₃ ⁻ (ppm)	ClO ₄ ⁻ (ppm)
Jan 10th	200,789	21,693	75,018	0*	0*	0,688	3,73
Jan 17th	160,807	14,119	92,915	0*	0*	0,679	4,173
Jan 24th	65,945	4,691	21,234	0*	0*	0,516	0,975
Jan 31th (1)	186,903	12,643	60,639	0*	0*	0,8	1,725
Jan 31th (2)	166,892	12,394	65,867	0*	0*	0,728	1,621
May 24th	6,178	9,323	13,183	0*	0*	0*	0*

724 *Zero values marked are categorized as > LOD MS but <LOQ CD and therefore depicted as 0.

725 *Random factors, variation and limitations*

726 Besides all mentioned factors, randomness and within source variability plays a
 727 large role as well. It is observed that there are large differences between
 728 samples originating from the same object taken at the same moment (from
 729 different spots). Two volunteers took all their samples from a single object. After
 730 analysis it is observed that in a large number of duplicates a coefficient of
 731 variance of 100% is obtained, the result of the absence (no detection) of an ion
 732 in one of the samples. This factor should always be taken into account when
 733 taking reference samples. Besides this, it is always possible to sample a
 734 contaminated spot on the object of interest, something that is more likely using
 735 a bigger sample frame as used by Walker et al. [8] and Lahoda et al. [9] or that
 736 the samples are taken from places that are not necessarily or excessively
 737 exposed to the ignition of fireworks.

738 Also, the amount of reference samples that have been taken is a factor involved
 739 in the outcome of the study. As mentioned before, 24 reference samples are
 740 taken for this study, a number that could be increased to obtain a more realistic
 741 view on the background levels prior to NYE.

742 Another factor of interest is the amount of locations sampled. As seen in **Fig. 3**,
 743 8 locations have been used for this study. These locations are not evenly
 744 distributed throughout the country. An increase of locations sampled and a more
 745 even distribution will help to make stronger claims based on the results.

746 *3.3.2 Alternative sources and environmental presence of ions*

747 It is described that the ions analyses may originated from the different types of
748 pyrotechnic compositions. But, as described before, there are several other ways
749 the ions can be present in the environment, and therefore in the samples.

750 Chloride may originate from the sea, as described by Ten Harkel [43] and David
751 and Crosbie [44]. The described measurement against slippery roads will also
752 introduce extra chloride to the environment. Research in China found out that
753 coal combustion (in winter) and open biomass burning (in summer) were
754 significant increasing factors to the chloride levels [45].

755 Other sources of nitrate, besides the pyrotechnics, are nitrogen rich manure
756 fertilizers and synthetic fertilizers [46]. Fertilizers will be used more in rural
757 areas than in city centres. Farmers tend to use fertilizers in spring (March and
758 April) and in fall (September and October). These time intervals are outside of
759 the time span of this study, but it should be taken into account for case work
760 within or following these intervals. Fertilizers will mostly contaminate the ground
761 water [46]. Therefore this could be a point of attention in areas where ground
762 water is used for agricultural or general purposed or where ground water
763 surfaces.

764 Several sources of sulfate are known and are to be considered. Polish research
765 found 3 main sources of sulfate in the environment, namely precipitation, peat
766 bogs, the decomposition of organic matters and micro bacterial activity [47].
767 Besides these factors, sulfate is also intrinsically present in several plaster or
768 gypsum based building materials [48].

769 Thiocyanate is, as mentioned before, pointed out as a proper marker for post
770 blast residues because of its low natural occurrence. Thiocyanate is used in
771 several industrial processes like the manufacturing of thiourea, metal
772 separations and electroplating. Besides this thiocyanate found as a pollutant in
773 waste waters from mining. Here it is the reaction product of the richly present
774 cyanide in the mining effluent and sulfur dioxide to remove the more harmful
775 cyanide [49]. Another natural occurrence of thiocyanate, in low concentrations,
776 is in the saliva of tobacco smokers [50]. These sources are considered as rather
777 rare, therefore thiocyanate is used as a marker for pyrotechnic activity.

778 Thiosulfate is, like thiocyanate, as a proper marker for post blast residues with a
779 low natural abundance. Thiosulfate is observed as aggressive corrosion agent
780 and a reactant in several industrial processes. The compound used to be used in
781 photographic development as a development agent and as an antichlor in the
782 paper industry. Besides this, it is encountered several medical and
783 pharmaceutical applications [51].

784 There is not much known on the natural occurrence of chlorate. It is found that
785 chlorate can be the product of the oxidation of an oxy-chlorine compound or
786 aqueous chlorine solution by ozone. Besides this, it is also found a by-product of
787 perchlorate formation as a result from the reaction between ozone and chlorine
788 containing precursors like chloride and hypochlorite. Until a couple of years ago,
789 the techniques were not sensitive and selective enough for the analysis of
790 chlorate, origins and environmental distributions are not known [19].

791 Perchlorate is found encountered in groundwater, soil and precipitation. Is
792 naturally formed the reaction between ozone and chlorine containing precursors
793 like chloride and hypochlorite, also resulting in chlorate as a by-product.
794 Concentrations found were very low, between 1 and 18 ng per litre (1.0×10^{-6} –
795 1.8×10^{-5} ppm) in ice and snow of the Canadian Arctic region, roughly a factor
796 100-1000 less as encountered in the NYEE study samples [19].

797 3.3.3 Interpretation

798 As described before, 'the effect' is prone to several factors. After reviewing the
799 results tendencies were observed. Most tendencies comply with the hypothesis
800 of the presumed NYEE. Therefore it could be stated that there is a noticeable
801 effect after the first of January (~80% of the cases). The results show that this
802 is not the case for all ions on all of the tested object types. As mentioned,
803 several factors play a role when looking at ions present at a certain object.

804 When reviewing the ions, regardless of with object they were recovered from, it
805 is observed that nitrate and chlorate in general are not following the pattern as
806 stated in the hypothesis. Both ions show a continuous increase (**Fig. 5**).

807 Taking the object in account (paragraph 3.2.4), a continuous increase of chloride
808 is observed on windows. Besides the natural occurrence of chloride, for example
809 in the so called 'sea breeze', the degradation of perchlorate present on the
810 windows, might lead to an increase of chloride as well.

811 The mentioned nitrate increase is present on windows. Besides the natural
812 appearances and human activities mentioned in paragraph 3.3.2, no explanation
813 for this increase is found. Nitrate is found to be stable on building materials.
814 When reviewing the raw data it is observed that the medians of all categories
815 are close, but a slightly different median for the first half of January samples is
816 found. The stable occurrence is more likely to be an effect of the data
817 presentation than a chemical property.

818 Sulfate displays a continuous increase on windows as well. This may be caused
819 by its presence in precipitation. It is probable that windows are prone to the
820 effects of precipitation as the three dominant ions are found in increasing levels
821 on this object type. Further it is noticeable that the levels remain stable on
822 traffic signs, this could be explained similar as the stable nitrate levels
823 mentioned before.

824 An increase of thiocyanate levels is observed in the second half of January on
825 traffic signs. The amount of samples that contained traces (< LOD MS) of
826 thiocyanate more than doubled. The samples originate from different locations.
827 Raw data analysis indicates that the objects containing thiocyanate in the first
828 half of January still contained the compound in the second half. The natural
829 occurrence (or human activities) mentioned in paragraph 3.3.2 do not seem to
830 be present near the locations of sample taking. No alternative explanation for
831 this increase is found.

832 Thiosulfate is found to be increased in the second half of January on traffic signs
833 and on building materials. The values found are still below the LOD of the CD,
834 but found using the MS. In both categories 3 samples tested positive on
835 thiosulfate. The difference in percentage is caused by the sample size differences
836 between the categories.

837 An increase of chlorate is observed on windows and chlorate levels found stable
838 on lamp posts. In both cases it might be possible that the before described
839 reduction of the present perchlorate is causing this. It is observed that on traffic
840 signs the amount of samples containing chlorate is lower in the first half of
841 January than for the reference samples and for the second half. For this
842 phenomenon no explanation is found. The possibility that chlorate ions are
843 reduced to chloride is not recognized in the trend of chloride. It is observed that
844 the amount of samples containing chlorate originating from building materials is
845 increased over the 3 time categories. The increase between the reference
846 samples and those from the first half of January might be explained by the
847 NYEE. For the increase between the first and the second half of January no
848 sound explanation could be found.

849 The tendencies observed for perchlorate are in line with the hypothesis on all
850 objects. Although the compound can be present in precipitation, the values
851 observed are higher than mentioned by Rao [19].

852 Analysis of the data shows that in 1.2% ($n = 1$) of the cases a statistically
853 significant effect is observed. The statistical analysis results are listed in
854 appendix II, **Table A1**. This effect was observed in the comparison of the
855 reference samples of perchlorate on lamp posts to the first half of January
856 samples. This shows that, even with the rather strict Bonferroni correction, there
857 is a significant increase of perchlorate after NYE on lamp posts. The results also
858 show an uncorrected significance level of 19%.

859 As mentioned before, the values in the second half of January are not back to
860 the values obtained from the reference samples for the ions thiocyanate,
861 thiosulfate, chlorate and perchlorate. This indicates that the experiment was
862 stopped before the effect was not observable anymore.

863 Together, it shows that there occur changes that we can define as the NYEE and
864 that this effect can be longer present than only the month of January. However,
865 the changes observed in this study, under the conditions as present at the time
866 of sampling taking, were in 98.8% of the times not significant (to place this in
867 perspective the applied strict Bonferroni correction should be kept in mind). The
868 significance of the NYEE is prone to many variables, as environmental
869 conditions, objects and specific ions.

870 **4. CONCLUSION**

871 This work investigated the presence and persistence of the so called 'New Year's
872 Eve Effect'. Three main questions were to be answered:

- 873 • Are values of certain chemicals related to fireworks in the environment
874 increased after NYE?
- 875 • Is the observed effect significant?
- 876 • How long does the effect persist?

877 To answer these questions samples were taken before and after NYE at several
878 locations on different types of objects placed in an open environment. The
879 samples were analysed using a state-of-the-art IC-ESI-MS method. The data
880 was statistically analysed and tendencies were investigated.

881 In most cases, an increase of ion concentrations after NYE was observed.
882 Tendencies of an increase after NYE and a decrease over the second half of
883 January were observed. Therefore there could be spoken of the presence of the
884 NYEE. The shifts in concentrations were determined not to be significant after
885 proper statistical analysis and correction ($\alpha = 0.000595$), with the exception of
886 one comparison. A significant increase of perchlorate on lamp posts was found
887 after NYE.

888 This gives insights on the extend of which the conditions present are influencing
889 the effect. It could be stated that the NYEE, is rarely significant under the
890 conditions present during this study, for example, the heavy rainfall in the start
891 of the year and the amount of fireworks ignited near the sampling sites. It is
892 very likely that different conditions will increase the significance.

893 It is shown that the value of the anions used as proper markers for post blast
894 residues are not back to the values as observed in the reference samples in the
895 second half of January indicates that the effect (under the conditions as present
896 during the study) persists longer than the month of January.

897 A fourth question could be touched upon: is the effect relevant to forensic
898 casework? This, however, will mostly depend on the case specific context. Since
899 we observed an effect after NYE in samples taken of places that are not
900 necessarily or excessively exposed to firework, it might be that an increase of
901 pyrotechnic activity will lead to higher significant differences. All in all, it is not
902 possible to determine the relevance of the effect in this study.

903 **5. FUTURE WORK**

904 Within the PyroProf project [52], this study was a pilot for the sampling strategy
905 and analysis method that will be used in a larger study, for which a nationwide
906 survey in the Netherlands will be carried out later in 2018. Based on this study
907 sampling strategies and data storage are improved and will be published in a
908 later stage of the PyroProf Project.

909 In order to obtain a more clear view of the NYEE it is recommended to perform a
910 more controlled testing to be aware of the impact of all possible effects. Besides
911 this, a cation method, which is currently being developed, will complement this
912 work, providing more information on the effect as a whole.

913 This study shows that there are large differences between the result of this
914 study and the used references in casework [8]. For this reason it is needed to
915 revise the way of interpretation. Concentrations of, previously, rare ions, are
916 found more often because of the newer and more sensitive techniques. Besides
917 this, the different sampling method, another country/region, and different
918 human activities will also play a role in the observed differences. All in all, it
919 means that the presence of the mentioned compounds does not directly
920 implicate the use of pyro techniques.

921

922

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975 [fD49Y9Vu6&ll=52.13035657329142%2C5.496451499999921&z=10](https://www.google.com/maps/d/edit?mid=1ugWFn52j6J0qM-GcUY-guP-fD49Y9Vu6&ll=52.13035657329142%2C5.496451499999921&z=10) [Accessed
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1086

1087 **SUPPLEMENTARY DATA**

- 1088 • Used chemical data (.xlsx)
- 1089 • Sample (NYEE) registration (.xlsx)
- 1090 • R Script: statistical analysis (.txt)
- 1091 • NFI SOP 161501 (.pdf)
- 1092 • Proposal PyroProf Project (.pdf)
- 1093

1094 **SUPPLEMENTARY DATA REQUESTS FOR:**

- 1095 • Raw MS data (.txt)
- 1096 • Raw IC data (.pdf)
- 1097 • Photos of the objects (.jpg)

1098 Correspondence and requests should be addressed to: Carlos Martín-Alberca
1099 (c.martin.alberca@nfi.minvenj.nl)

1100 **APPENDICES**

1101 **Appendix I Overview of the presence of all critical ions per object**

1102

1103 **Fig. A1** Abundance of the concentration categories on windows of all critical ions, divided over
 1104 three time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and
 1105 from January 16th till January 31st.

1106

1107 **Fig. A2** Abundance of the concentration categories on traffic signs of all critical ions, divided over
 1108 three time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and
 1109 from January 16th till January 31st.

1110

1111

1112 **Fig. A3** Abundance of the concentration categories on building materials of all critical ions, divided
 1113 over three time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January
 1114 15th and from January 16th till January 31st.

1115

1116 **Fig. A4** Abundance of the concentration categories on lamp posts of all critical ions, divided
 1117 over three time intervals: reference samples/ref (before NYE), from the January 1st till January 15th and
 1118 from January 16th till January 31st.

1119

1120 **Appendix II Statistical analysis**

1121

1122 **Table A1** Results of the statistical analysis. Per row the significance difference between two time
 1123 intervals (comparison: R = reference, 1 = first half of January, 2 = second half of January) is
 1124 calculated for a specific ion on a specific object. The calculated P values are obtained using the
 1125 Wilcoxon rank sum test. The corrected, and eventually used, P values are obtained after
 1126 performing the Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons. The line printed in **bold** represents
 1127 the only significant change of background levels. The statistical analysis is performed on the
 1128 quantitative indication results of the CD (ppm). Whenever a sample was marked with '> LOD MS' a
 1129 value of 0.0001 was used in order to differentiate between low trace compounds and not detected
 1130 compounds.

1131

Object	Anion	Comparison	Z value	P value	Corrected P value
Window	Chlorate	R.1	3,168	0,000767	0,064462
Window	Chlorate	R.2	0,0337	0,002416	0,202944
Window	Chlorate	1.2	0,39437	0,3467	1
Trafficsign	Chlorate	R.1	-1,9899	0,9767	1
Trafficsign	Chlorate	R.2	-1,2839	0,1992	1
Trafficsign	Chlorate	1.2	-1,3069	0,9044	1
Buildingmaterial	Chlorate	R.1	0,42925	0,3339	1
Buildingmaterial	Chlorate	R.2	-	-	-
Buildingmaterial	Chlorate	1.2	0,53748	0,2955	1
Lamppost	Chlorate	R.1	0,78874	0,2151	1
Lamppost	Chlorate	R.2	0,40444	0,6859	1
Lamppost	Chlorate	1.2	1,3303	0,09171	1
Window	Chloride	R.1	3,1901	0,001711	0,143732
Window	Chloride	R.2	3,2387	0,001201	0,100884
Window	Chloride	1.2	-0,94486	0,8276	1
Trafficsign	Chloride	R.1	0,58554	0,2791	1
Trafficsign	Chloride	R.2	-0,18257	0,8551	1
Trafficsign	Chloride	1.2	0	0,5	1
Buildingmaterial	Chloride	R.1	1,633	0,5124	1
Buildingmaterial	Chloride	R.2	-0,7746	0,4386	1
Buildingmaterial	Chloride	1.2	1,8074	0,03535	1
Lamppost	Chloride	R.1	1,2773	0,1008	1
Lamppost	Chloride	R.2	-0,24256	0,8083	1
Lamppost	Chloride	1.2	1,285	0,09939	1
Window	Nitrate	R.1	0,98387	0,1626	1
Window	Nitrate	R.2	2,7053	0,006825	0,5733
Window	Nitrate	1.2	-2,0749	0,981	1
Trafficsign	Nitrate	R.1	-2,1958	0,9859	1
Trafficsign	Nitrate	R.2	-1,4606	0,1441	1
Trafficsign	Nitrate	1.2	-0,6455	0,7407	1
Buildingmaterial	Nitrate	R.1	1,0206	0,1537	1
Buildingmaterial	Nitrate	R.2	0	1	1
Buildingmaterial	Nitrate	1.2	1,4217	0,07756	1

Object	Anion	Comparison	Z value	P value	Corrected P value
Lamppost	Nitrate	R.1	-1,0712	0,858	1
Lamppost	Nitrate	R.2	-0,54502	0,5857	1
Lamppost	Nitrate	1.2	-1,0745	0,8587	1
Window	Perchlorate	R.1	2,5822	0,004907	0,412188
Window	Perchlorate	R.2			
Window	Perchlorate	1.2	-0,70165	0,7586	1
Trafficsign	Perchlorate	R.1	1,0392	0,1493	1
Trafficsign	Perchlorate	R.2	0,4714	0,6374	1
Trafficsign	Perchlorate	1.2	0,60093	0,2739	1
Buildingmaterial	Perchlorate	R.1	0,82496	0,2047	1
Buildingmaterial	Perchlorate	R.2	-0,53452	0,2047	1
Buildingmaterial	Perchlorate	1.2	1,6525	0,04921	1
Lamppost	Perchlorate	R.1	3,7203	9,95E-05	0,008356
Lamppost	Perchlorate	R.2	-	-	-
Lamppost	Perchlorate	1.2	3,1154	0,000918	0,077146
Window	Sulfate	R.1	2,9529	0,001574	0,132216
Window	Sulfate	R.2	3,2397	0,001197	0,100548
Window	Sulfate	1.2	-1,2216	0,8891	1
Trafficsign	Sulfate	R.1	-0,29317	0,6153	1
Trafficsign	Sulfate	R.2	0,7303	0,4652	1
Trafficsign	Sulfate	1.2	-0,64621	0,7409	1
Buildingmaterial	Sulfate	R.1	2,2454	0,01237	1
Buildingmaterial	Sulfate	R.2	-0,77784	0,4367	1
Buildingmaterial	Sulfate	1.2	1,9386	0,2627	1
Lamppost	Sulfate	R.1	0,35924	0,3597	1
Lamppost	Sulfate	R.2	-0,68167	0,4954	1
Lamppost	Sulfate	1.2	1,1114	0,1332	1
Window	Thiocyanate	R.1	1,1723	0,1205	1
Window	Thiocyanate	R.2	-0,39943	0,6896	1
Window	Thiocyanate	1.2	1,7358	0,0413	1
Trafficsign	Thiocyanate	R.1	-0,0866	0,5345	1
Trafficsign	Thiocyanate	R.2	-	-	
Trafficsign	Thiocyanate	1.2	-1,6525	0,9508	1
Buildingmaterial	Thiocyanate	R.1	-	-	-
Buildingmaterial	Thiocyanate	R.2	-	-	-
Buildingmaterial	Thiocyanate	1.2	-	-	-
Lamppost	Thiocyanate	R.1	1,642	0,0503	1
Lamppost	Thiocyanate	R.2	0,43644	0,6625	1
Lamppost	Thiocyanate	1.2	1,7826	0,03732	1
Window	Thiosulfate	R.1	-	-	-
Window	Thiosulfate	R.2	-	-	-
Window	Thiosulfate	1.2	1,6757	0,0469	1
Trafficsign	Thiosulfate	R.1	-	-	-
Trafficsign	Thiosulfate	R.2	-	-	-
Trafficsign	Thiosulfate	1.2	-	-	-

Object	Anion	Comparison	Z value	P value	Corrected P value
Buildingmaterial	Thiosulfate	R.1	0,12199	0,4515	1
Buildingmaterial	Thiosulfate	R.2			
Buildingmaterial	Thiosulfate	1.2	-0,45069	0,6739	1
Lamppost	Thiosulfate	R.1	-	-	-
Lamppost	Thiosulfate	R.2	-	-	-
Lamppost	Thiosulfate	1.2	0,83686	0,2013	1

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